

15+

Interactive
Sessions

10+

Keynote
Lectures

40+

Scientific
Sessions

3+

Workshops

30+

Posters

B2B

Meetings

PHARMA CONFERENCE 2018

MIDDLE EAST PHARMACY AND PHARMACEUTICAL CONFERENCE

September 24-25, 2018

Abu Dhabi, UAE

“Global Innovations and Recent Advances In Pharmaceutical Science”

Media Partners

Email: pharma.pharmaceutical.2018@gmail.com

Website: <https://pharma.pharmaceuticalconferences.com/>

**Panel Discussions
&
B2B Meetings**

What's in store for 2018?

PHARMA CONFERENCE 2018

Our Scientific Editorials Board

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Journals Supported By

- Research & Reviews in Middle East Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Conference
- International Journal of Drug Development and Research
- Journal of Pharmaceutics & Drug Delivery Research
- Journal of Nanomedicine & Nanotechnology

Tentative Agenda

Day 1 September 24, 2018	
	Opening Ceremony
	Conference Souvenir Launch
	New Perspective frontiers in the area of Middle East Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Conference
	Keynote Forum (& Exhibitions Full day)
	(Panel discussions and Reviews)
	Coffee Break: Networking & Refreshments
	Group Photo
	Speaker Forum
	Sessions Chair's Introduction
	Session 1: Drug Discovery & Development
	Session 2: Novel Drug Delivery System
	Session 3: Pharmaceutical Nanotechnology
	Session 4: Bioavailability & Bioequivalence
	Session 5: Pharmacogenomics
	Session 6: Pharmaceutical Formulations
	Panel discussions and Reviews
	Lunch Break
	Session 7: Clinical Research
	Session 8: Advances in Pharmaceutical Packaging
	Panel discussions and Reviews
	Young Research Forum
	(Panel discussions and Reviews)
	Coffee Break: Networking & Refreshments
	B2B Meetings

Day 2 September 25, 2018	
	Opening Ceremony
	Conference Souvenir Launch
	New Perspective frontiers in the area of Middle East Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Conference
	Keynote Forum (& Exhibitions Full day)
	(Panel discussions and Reviews)
	Coffee Break: Networking & Refreshments
	Group Photo
	Speaker Forum
	Sessions Chair's Introduction
	Session 9: Pharmaceutical Analysis
	Session 10: Quality Assurance & Quality control
	Session 11: Pharmacokinetics & pharmacodynamics
	Panel discussions and Reviews
	Lunch Break
	Session 12: Pharmacology & Toxicology
	Session 13: Drug Targeting and Drug development
	Session 14: Pharmacovigilance
	Panel discussions and Reviews
	Young Research Forum
	(Panel discussions and Reviews)
	Coffee Break: Networking & Refreshments
	B2B Meetings

Venue & Accommodation

**Radisson Blu Hotel Abu
Dhabi Yas Island
Yas Plaza, P.O.Box 93725
Abu Dhabi, UAE**

Route Map

Important Dates

Abstract Submission Opens: **December 01, 2017**

Registration Opens: **January 01, 2018**

Early Bird Registration: **May 25, 2018**

On Spot Registration: **September 24, 2018**

MAIL US TO KNOW MORE!

For Abstract Submission Guidelines | For Reserving your slot | Proposals | Registration | Posters | Accommodations

No doubt you have lots of queries...

Why not get in touch..!

Drop us your query with details and we will call you right away

For Queries

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